

Statistical Overview of Union County Car Crashes

Sources: United States Census Bureau 2017 Population Data, Ohio State Highway Patrol Crash Statistics 2018.

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Crashes & Population Statistics by Township

The Ohio State Highway Patrol provides 3 statistical databases of crash statistics from 2018 to the public upon request. The United States Census Bureau provides population estimates as late as 2017. With the exception of Paris Township, the errors that the estimate may cause, both because it's an estimate, and because it's one year apart from the statistics being listed, should have very minimal impact on the accuracy of the report.

Union County Township Crash Statistics & Population [2018]

County	# of Crashes ¹	Population ²	Crashes to Population %
Allen Township	96	2,479	3.87%
Jerome Township	75	5,593	1.34%
Paris Township	58	25,606	0.23%
Millcreek Township	22	1,426	1.54%
Dover Township	21	2,632	0.80%
York Township	17	1,455	1.17%
Leesburg Township	20	1,527	1.31%
Union Township	17	1,763	0.96%
Liberty Township	13	2,132	0.61%
Claibourne Township	10	3,777	0.26%
Taylor Township	14	1,703	0.82%
Darby Township	11	2,219	0.50%
Jackson Township	8	1,057	0.76%
Washington Township	8	901	0.89%
Union County	390	56,741	3.87%

¹ 2018 Ohio State Highway Patrol Crash Statistics (i)

² 2017 Population Statistics, not 2018. (United States Census Bureau) (i)

Crashes and Population by Township | Figures

Union County % of Total Crashes & % of Total Population.

of Crashes to Population [Ratio]

Crash Severity & Light Conditions | Figures

Crash Severity

Crashes per Light Condition

Weather & Road Condition | Figures

Road Condition

Crashes per Weather Condition

Other Conditions Relating to Crashes | Figures

Other Factors Relating to Crashes & their Contribution to the % of the Total Crashes

Related Too:

Other Factors Relating to Crashes & their Contribution to the % of the Total Crashes FIGURE 2

Allen & Jerome Township's High Rate of Crash

Allen Township and Jerome Township are the locations of 38.97% of Union County car crashes, despite their population combined being only 14.23% of Union County.

It is notable that Jerome Township does have the 2nd highest populous in Union County with 5,593 residents, coming behind Paris Township which has 25,606 residents. The data opposes the easily-made suspicion that the statistical difference in car crashes is caused by a larger than the average population.

The data opposes the same suspicion in Allen Township, as it only contains 4.57% of Union Counties population but is the location of 24.62% of the counties car crashes, and no other township matches this even with similar populations.

% of Allen Township Crashes, % of Jerome Township Crashes and % of Union County Crashes

This figure shows us of Allen Township, Jerome Township, and Union County as a whole, what % of crashes had relations to the listed factors in each individual. The most significant statistical anomaly in this figure is that 21.67% of Jerome Townships crashes are related to teens, compared to Union Counties 14.10%, and Allen Townships 13% ³This increase in teen-related accidents increases Jerome Townships percentage of Union County Crashes by 3%.

³ Due to the relatively low population of both Allen and Jerome Township, random chance may account for 0-60% of the increase in crashes. Even then, the increase is still high, and presumably not without cause.

Allen Township, Jerome Township, and Union County Conditional Comparison.

Percents were made conditionally for the total crashes in Allen Township, Jerome Township, and Union County. The conditions at the time of each crash were taken (weather, the road conditions, the road contour, and the light condition). The only significant differences are with Jerome Township, the road contour listed as "Road Straight Grade" had a +21.79% difference to that of Union County, and the Lighting Condition listed as "Daylight" had a +14.71% difference compared to that of Union County.

Related To/Condition at Time of Crash	% of Allen's Crashes	% of Jerome's Crashes	% of Union Counties Crashes ⁴	Allen / Union County % Difference	Jerome / Union County % Difference
Weather Clear	58.70%	63.33%	62.67%	-3.97%	+0.66%
Weather Cloudy	18.48%	28.33%	18.66%	-0.18%	+9.67%
Weather Rain	13.04%	5.00%	11.14%	1.90%	-6.14%
Weather Snow	7.61%	0.00%	3.62%	3.99%	-3.62%
Weather Sleet/Hail	2.17%	1.67%	1.95%	0.22%	-0.28%
Road Dry	66.30%	78.33%	73.26%	-6.96%	+5.07%
Road Wet	25.00%	20.00%	20.61%	4.39%	-0.61%
Road Snow	4.35%	1.67%	2.51%	1.84%	-0.84%
Road Slush	1.09%	0.00%	0.84%	0.25%	-0.84%
Road Straight Level	59.78%	58.33%	59.61%	0.17%	-1.28%
Road Curve Level	8.70%	10.00%	8.36%	0.34%	+1.64%
Road Straight Grade	27.17%	23.33%	25.63%	1.54%	+21.79%
Road Curve Grade	4.35%	8.33%	6.13%	-1.78%	+2.20%
Road Dark, Not Lit	29.35%	26.67%	35.20%	-5.85%	-8.53%
Road Dark, Lit	6.52%	5.00%	5.03%	1.49%	-0.03%
Road Daylight	46.74%	66.67%	51.96%	-5.22%	+14.71%
Road Dawn/Dusk	17.39%	1.67%	7.82%	9.57%	-6.15%

⁴ Allen and Jerome Township's data was not removed when calculating Union Counties conditionally sorted %'s to total.

Allen Township, Jerome Township, and Union County Conditional Comparison | Figures

Allen/Jerome Township to Union County % Difference (Conditions Related too/Present during crash % to Total Crashes for Allen/Jerome to Union Total Crashes %)

AJ Related too:

Allen % Difference and Jerome % Difference

